

Gültekin (2021) paper has a substantial number of identical data with the 20-year earlier Demirag (2001) paper

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This comment was originally published in PubPeer, 2022 February:

<https://pubpeer.com/publications/8150B66EC0289FA4BF7C9ADB1C48A9#1>

The address of this version is: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19790681>

Gültekin et al. have not responded to the PubPeer critique by 2026.

This analysis compares two controlled trial reports:

1. Gültekin Y, Güzel A, Karakaya A, Beşoğul Y.

Combined effects of the implementation of magnesium and ascorbic acid on myocardial ischemia-reperfusion in open heart surgery.

Anatolian Current Medical Journal. 2021;3(4):319–326.

<https://doi.org/10.38053/acmj.982137>

2. Demirag K, Askar FZ, Uyar M, Cevik A, Ozmen D, Mutaf I, Bayindir O.

The protective effects of high dose ascorbic acid and diltiazem on myocardial ischaemia-reperfusion injury.

Middle East J. Anaesthesiol. 2001;16(1):67-79.

<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/11281049>

<https://zenodo.org/records/8287478>

In 2021, Gültekin et al. published a controlled trial on the effects of vitamin C alone, and of vitamin C together with Mg, for patients undergoing CABG [1].

In 2001, Demirag et al. published a controlled trial on the effects of vitamin C alone, and of vitamin C together with diltiazem, for patients undergoing CABG [2]. Thus, the patients were similar to those examined by Gültekin and the design was similar except for using diltiazem instead of Mg.

Gültekin's Table 3 shows the lactate dehydrogenase (LDH) levels in each of the three groups before and after surgery (see below).

For example, in the Group K (control), the LDH level before surgery was 418.2 ± 124.3 (SD) [1].

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17085738> Reports on scurvy uploaded to Zenodo by Harri Hemilä

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19791426> Misleading and erroneous papers on vitamin C; a list by Harri Hemilä

The identical finding 418.2 ± 124.3 (SD), also for LDH, was published for the Group AA + D (Ascorbic acid + diltiazem) in Table 2 by Demirag (2001) [2] (see below).

It is highly unlikely that two vitamin C studies of CABG find identical mean and SD combination with 4-digit accuracy by chance.

All six SD values for the LDH published in Gültekin's Table 3 [1] are identical with 4-digit accuracy to the six SD values reported 20 years earlier in Demirag's Table 2 [2]. Only the order of the SD values for the three groups has been changed (see below).

Similarly, five of the six LDH mean values are identical in those two tables. The only difference is in Gültekin's time point 1 for Group CM (497.8) which is slightly different from Demirag's preop level in Group AA (498.9).

There is also data in **Gültekin's Table 2** which is identical to data previously published by Demirag. Gültekin et al. [1] reported that the mean surgery time was 358, 351, and 315 minutes in the three groups (see below). In their Table 1, Demirag et al. [2] reported that the mean surgery time was 358, 351, and 315 minutes in the three groups. In this case the order is identical in the two papers (see below). In addition, all the other findings in Gültekin's Table 2 are also identical or very close to those reported in Demirag's Table 1.

In **Table 4, Gültekin** reported malondialdehyde (MDA) levels. On time points 2 and 3, all the six SD values are identical with the six SD values for time points 2 and 3 in Demirag's Table 3 (see below). In addition, two of the six mean values are identical in the two papers (3.64 and 2.55).

Reporting of **cardiac arrhythmia** was also identical in the two papers. Gültekin (2021) wrote that "arrhythmia requiring intervention was observed in six patients in Group K [control], three patients in Group C [vitC], and one patient in Group CM [vitC+Mg]" (p 322). Demirag (2001) wrote that "VF [ventricular fibrillation] after declamping was positive in 3, 1, and 6 patients in the groups AA [vitC], AA + D [vitC+diltiazem] and C [control] respectively" (p 74).

Finally, Gültekin (2021) and Demirag (2001) both used the same age range as the inclusion criterion: 44 to 75 years. This identity of range is not necessarily quite puzzling. However, given the great changes in the age distribution in society over the previous 20 years and investigating different population groups, **it seems implausible that the same age range leads to the same mean and SD values for age**. For their patients, Gültekin reported mean age 63.86 (SD 8.59) years [1], whereas 20 years earlier Demirag reported that their patients had mean age 63.8 (SD 8.5) years [2].

It does not seem plausible that such a large number of identical findings in two vitamin C papers is explained by chance.

Same data on LDH:

Table 3 in Gültekin (2021) [1]

Table 3. CK-MB and LDH levels of the groups				
	Group K (n=15) (mean±std)	Group C (n=15) (mean±std)	Group CM (n=15) (mean±std)	P value
LDH 1 (m/l)	418.2±124.3	486.2±114.1	497.8±182.7	>0.05
LDH 2 (m /l)	992.1±225.1*	1013.0±306.9*	1037.2±256.6*	>0.05
std: standard deviation. * P<0.001 compared with the preoperative value.				

Table 2 in Demirag (2001) [2]

*Table 2:
Preoperative and postoperative plasma ascorbic acid and
cardiac enzyme levels (mean ± SD).*

	Group C (Control)	Group AA (Ascorbic acid)	Group AA + D (Ascorbic acid + diltiazem)
Preop LDH (UL ⁻¹)	486.2 ± 114.1	498.9 ± 182.7	418.2 ± 124.3
Postop LDH	1013.0 ± 306.9**	1037.2 ± 256.6**	992.1 ± 225.1**

AA = Ascorbic acid; CPK = creatine phosphokinase; CK-MB = MB isoenzyme of creatine kinase; LDH = lactate dehydrogenase. **P<0.001 vs preoperative level.

Same data on operation time, CPB time, CC time, and bypass grafts count:

Table 2 in Gültekin (2021) [1]

Table 2. Intraoperative parameters of patients				
	Group K (n=15) (mean±std)	Group C (n=15) (mean±std)	Group CM (n=15) (mean±std)	P value
Operation time (min)	358.0±55.9	351.0±55.6	315.0±57.2	>0.05
CPB time (min)	127.2±39.4	132.9±32.1	125.6±33.1	>0.05
CC time (min)	70.9±26.9	85.0±28.2	81.4±23.1	>0.05
Bypass grafts count	3.7±0.4	3.8±0.4	3.5±0.8	>0.05

CPB: Cardiopulmonary bypass; CC: cross clamp; std: standard deviation; min: minute.

Table 1 in Demirag (2001) [2]

*Table 1:
Preoperative patient characteristics and operative data (mean ± SD).*

	Group C (Control)	Group AA (Ascorbic acid)	Group AA + D (Ascorbic acid + diltiazem)
Duration of operation (min)	358 ± 56	351 ± 56	315 ± 57
Duration of CPB (min)	127 ± 39	133 ± 32	128 ± 33
Cross-clamping time (min)	71 ± 27	85 ± 28	81 ± 23
Grafts/patient	3.7 ± 0.4	3.8 ± 0.4	3.5 ± 0.8

BSA = Basal surface area; EF = ejection fraction; CPB = cardiopulmonary bypass.

Same SD values for MDA on time points 2 and 3

Table 4 in Gültekin (2021) [1]

Table 4. MDA levels of the groups			
	Group K (n=15) (mean±std)	Group C (n=15) (mean±std)	Group CM (n=15) (mean±std)
MDA 2 (nmol/g)	3.04±0.88*	2.54±0.74 [‡]	2.55±0.62 ^{‡§}
MDA 3 (nmol/g)	3.64±0.81 ^{††}	2.87±0.61 [‡]	2.62±0.68 ^{‡§}

Table 3 in Demirag (2001) [2]

*Table 3:
MDA levels obtained from arterial and coronary sinus blood (mean ± SD)*

	Group C (Control)	Group AA (Ascorbic acid)	Group AA + D (Ascorbic acid + diltiazem)
Art-MDA ₂	3.44 ± 0.88*#	2.32 ± 0.74*	2.55 ± 0.62*
Art-MDA ₃	3.64 ± 0.81*#	2.73 ± 0.61*	2.72 ± 0.68*